

Copper(III) as an Oxidative Titrant for Alanine, 2-aminobutyric Acid and Arginine monohydrochloride

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PREPARATION, standardisation and applications of tellurato cuprate(III) have been described in earlier publications¹⁻³. The present communication describes the microdetermination of alanine, 2-aminobutyric acid and arginine monohydrochloride using Cu(III).

butyric acid and arginine monohydrochloride were of B.D.H. biochemical grade.

Procedure : An aliquot of the aqueous solution containing 1.0-3.5 μ moles of amino acid was added to an excess of Cu(III) reagent ($1.56 \times 10^{-4} \mu$ moles). The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate for 15 minutes, cooled and the unconsumed Cu(III) determined as described earlier¹. Total volume of solution mixture was kept 20 ml. Blank experiments were also conducted under identical conditions. The results are given in Table 1.

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TABLE I—OXIDATION OF ALANINE, 2-AMINO BUTYRIC ACID AND ARGININE MONOHYDROCHLORIDE USING TELLURATO COPPER (III) REAGENT

Amino Acid	Amount of amino acid taken μ mole.	Copper (III) consumed equiv./mole of amino acid*			Error %
		a	b	c	
Alanine	2.94	2.42	5.56	19.90	-0.5
2-Aminobutyric acid	2.52	1.64	6.70	25.96	-0.15
Arginine monohydrochloride	1.27	2.52	9.00	55.82	-0.32

* Mean of six results.

- (a) Determination of Cu(III) immediately after adding the amino acid solution.
- (b) Determination of Cu(III) after allowing the solution mixture to stand for 15 minutes at room temperature.
- (c) Determination of Cu(III) after refluxing and cooling the reaction mixture for 15 minutes.

It has been found that alanine, 2-aminobutyric acid and arginine monohydrochloride required 20,26 and 56 equivalents of the oxidant respectively for their complete oxidation. The results are reproducible within $\pm 0.5\%$. Tellurate does not interfere as oxidant, since Cu(III) being a stronger oxidant, reoxidises any tellurite that may be formed in the reaction mixture. It was also observed that refluxing and cooling of the reaction mixture is essential to complete the oxidation, as determination of Cu(III) immediately after mixing or after allowing to stand for 15 minutes at room temperature gave erroneous results indicating incomplete oxidation.

Experimental

Materials : All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. Telluratocuprate(III) reagent was prepared and standardised as described earlier¹. Alanine, 2-amino-

Binary and Ternary Chelates of Sc(III), Y(III) and La(III) with Ethylenediamine tetraacetic Acid as Primary Ligand and Substituted Salicylic Acids as Secondary Ligands

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ETHYLENEDIAMINETETRAACETIC acid (edta) behaves as a polydentate ligand and forms strong complexes with metal ions in solution at low pH values¹⁻⁴, which remain stable at higher pH as well. Thus, edta has widely been used as one of the constituents in the study of a number of ternary complexing systems.

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The work described here relates to a study of ternary complex formation of several tripositive metal ions viz. Sc(III), Y(III) and La(III) with edta as a primary ligand and 5-chlorosalicylic acid (csa) or 3,5-dibromosalicylic acid (dbsa) as secondary ligands (H_2L) by pH-metric titration technique^{5,6}. All the experiments were carried out at 25° and ionic strength of 0.1 (KNO₃) in 50% (v/v) aqueous-ethanol medium.

It may be mentioned here that ternary complexes of these secondary ligands with several bivalent metal ions and 2, 2' bipyridine^{7,8}, 1,10 phenanthroline⁹, and nitrilotriacetic acid^{10,11} as primary ligands have earlier been reported from these laboratories.

Experimental

Materials :

Nitrate solutions of Sc(III), Y(III) and La(III), and of NaOH and HNO₃ were prepared using reagent grade chemicals and standardized. Aqueous solutions of KNO₃ and edta, and ethanolic solutions of csa and dbsa were prepared by direct weighing. Redistilled absolute ethanol (BCPW) was used wherever necessary.

Apparatus :

pH measurements were made at 25° using expanded scale pH meter (Electronic Corp. of India) with glass-calomel electrode assembly supplied with the instrument.

Procedure :

The pH-metric titrations of binary and ternary complexing systems, the composition of the titration mixtures and the calculations were same as described earlier¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

Values of proton ligand stability constants obtained by average value method are recorded in Table 1, which are in agreement with earlier findings¹⁰. Only 1 : 1 binary metal-chelates of csa and dbsa could be studied. Higher complexing species or hydroxo species likely to be formed after this stage could not be examined due to occurrence of opacity/turbidity/precipitation.

The stability order of metal chelates with respect to various ligands are : dbsa > csa, while those with respect to metal ions are : Sc(III) > Y(III) > La(III).

The values of $\log K_{M\text{-edta-L}}$ [$K_{M\text{-edta-L}}$ = mixed ligand formation constant in M-edta-L systems] is less than $\log K_1$ [K_1 = first step formation constant of binary complexes with secondary ligands]. During mixed ligand complex formation, the coulombic repulsion between (M-edta)⁻¹ species and the incoming ligand L²⁻ lowers the stability of mixed ligand

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS IN BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXING SYSTEM, 25° ; $\mu=1.0$ (KNO₃)

Equilibria	Log equilibrium constants
$H_2L(\text{ligand})=csa$	
$H^+ + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons LH^-$	11.56 ± 0.09
$LH^- + H^+ \rightleftharpoons LH_2$	3.11 ± 0.05
$Sc^{3+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons ScL^+$	9.07 ± 0.03
$Y^{3+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons YL^+$	8.48 ± 0.03
$La^{3+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons LaL^+$	7.75 ± 0.03
$(Sc\ edta)^- + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (Sc\ edta\ L)^{3-}$	5.34 ± 0.02
$(Y\ edta)^- + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (Y\ edta\ L)^{3-}$	5.08 ± 0.02
$(La\ edta)^- + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (La\ edta\ L)^{3-}$	4.88 ± 0.02
$H_2L = dbsa$	
$H^+ + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons LH^-$	12.05 ± 0.06
$LH^- + H^+ \rightleftharpoons LH_2$	2.86 ± 0.09
$Sc^{3+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons ScL^+$	9.68 ± 0.01
$Y^{3+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons YL^+$	8.84 ± 0.07
$La^{3+} + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons LaL^+$	8.20 ± 0.07
$(Sc\ edta)^- + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (Sc\ edta\ L)^{3-}$	5.78 ± 0.02
$(Y\ edta)^- + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (Y\ edta\ L)^{3-}$	5.57 ± 0.01
$(La\ edta)^- + L^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (La\ edta\ L)^{3-}$	5.38 ± 0.02

complexes. On the other hand formation of ML species, is accompanied by coulombic attraction between M³⁺ and the incoming ligand L²⁻ which justifies $\log K_1 > \log K_{M\text{-edta-L}}$. The stability order with respect to metal ions and the ligands follow the same pattern as those in corresponding binary complexing systems.

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Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) Complexes with 3(2'-furoyl) 2-Cyano Ethyl Crotonate

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IN the programme of preparing complexes of rare and higher co-ordination numbers with divalent first transition series metal ions, polydentate chelating ligands are being synthesised since such ligands dominate the area of higher co-ordination polyhedra in scope, numbers and also from kinetic and thermodynamic stability point of view. Particularly, the compact nature of polydentate schiff's bases make them more effective in attaining high co-ordination structure. Earlier complexation behaviour of bi, tri and tetradentate schiff's bases have been reported¹⁻⁵. In this communication a number of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and

Zn(II) complexes with a bidentate ligand derived from condensation of furfuraldehyde and ethyl cyanoacetate will be presented.

Experimental

Synthesis of the Ligands : Furfuraldehyde and ethyl cyanoacetate in 1:1 proportion were mixed with 1 cc of piperidine as base and refluxed for 6-8 hours. The contents were poured into a 10% solution of hydrochloric acid and kept standing for six days. Pinkish-violet crystalline compound separated out which was filtered, washed with ether and dried in vacuum.

Preparation of Complexes : Ethanolic solution of different metal salts were treated with ethanolic solution of the ligand in 1:2 proportion and the resulting solution refluxed for one hour. On keeping the resulting solution overnight crystalline compounds separated. These were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuum desiccator.

Metal and nitrogen in the complexes were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in M/1000 acetone solution using Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on solid specimens at room temperature by the Guoy method. I. R. spectra were recorded using Perkin-Elmer-337 and Beckman I. R.-12 spectrophotometers. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Hilger-watt uvispeck spectrophotometer with M/100 chloroform solution of the complexes. Analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility and spectral data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compounds	M. P. (°C)	Λ_M (mhos. cm ²)	μ_{eff} (B. M.)	% metal		% nitrogen		Electronic spectra ν_{max} in k. k. (€)
				Found.	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
CoCl ₂ L ₂	165	6.5	4.9	11.25	11.51	5.22	5.47	18.8 (35), 8.0 (16)
CoBr ₂ L ₂	185	7.3	5.0	9.48	9.82	4.25	4.66	19.2 (38), 8.0 (16)
Co(NO ₃) ₂ L ₂	180	6.8	5.2	10.15	10.43	9.58	9.91	19.4 (40), 8.2 (18)
NiCl ₂ L	202	7.4	—	18.11	18.30	4.02	4.36	16.5 (50)
NiBr ₂ L	198	8.2	—	14.15	14.37	3.05	3.42	17.4 (54)
Ni(NO ₃) ₂ L	176	8.5	—	15.46	15.71	10.91	11.24	18.0 (55)
CuCl ₂ L ₂	205	5.8	1.78	12.05	12.30	5.22	5.42	14.8 (30)
CuBr ₂ L ₂	196	6.2	1.80	10.21	10.51	4.31	4.63	15.0 (35)
Cu(NO ₃) ₂ L ₂	190	6.5	1.82	10.85	11.15	9.56	9.83	15.3 (40)
ZnCl ₂ L ₂	185	8.2	—	12.26	12.61	5.20	5.40	—
ZnBr ₂ L ₂	176	8.4	—	10.45	10.78	4.28	4.62	—
Zn(NO ₃) ₂ L ₂	183	7.5	—	11.21	11.44	9.56	9.80	—

L=3 (2'-Furoyl)-2-cyano ethyl crotonate.